

Research Article

ALL-TURKIC LEXICAL LAYER IN THE UZBEK DIALECTS OF ZARAFSHAN OASIS

Linguistics

Keywords: dialect, all-Turkic word, assimilated word, dictionary, lexical layer, ethno linguistics, etymological, root word, historical development of language.

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Abstract

The study of the lexical structure of Uzbek dialects, including the Uzbek dialects of the Zarafshan oasis, is of great importance in determining the history of development of the Uzbek language, the ways of development of its basic dialects. It should be noted that the historical and etymological analysis of the lexical layer of the Uzbek language will help to determine its relationship with the Turkic languages, the influence of sister and non-sister languages on the Uzbek language. It is known that when examining the lexical structure of the language from the etymological point of view, first of all, historically and genetically the words that belong to the Uzbek language, i.e. all-Turkic words, are identified, and then words borrowed from other languages are identified. Lexical layers in dialects are studied in the same way. According to the linguistic analysis of the factual materials collected on the dialects of this region, the main part of the dialect of this region consists of all-Turkic words, the rest - words borrowed from Persian-Tajik, Arabic, Russian and Western European languages. Based on this theory in the study of the lexical structure of the dialects of the Zarafshan oasis dialects, we also think about all-Turkic dialectal words in this article.

According to the analysis of the dialects of the Zarafshan oasis, the main part of the vocabulary of the dialects of the region consists of all-Turkic words. As in the Uzbek language, many lexical units in the lexicon of Uzbek dialects, including the dialects of the Zarafshan oasis, are ancient words. These ancient words are called primitive words, primitive Turkic words in the literature: “primitive words are words that belong to the language itself. Therefore, lexemes belonging to the group of primitive Turkic words belong to the same language according to their genetic source. The original words are usually very old” [2, p.36]. Many of them still exist in the vernacular today, and when studied comparatively with ancient written sources, they are indeed evidence of a long period of time. Such words are present in all Turkic languages and they are a dictionary of these languages. Since they belong to all Turkic languages, they are words belonging to the all-Turkic lexical layer. Indeed, “a distinctive feature of the main vocabulary of Turkic languages is their commonality for all Turkic languages” [1, pp.118-119]. The similarity in Turkic languages does not mean that they are passed from one language to another, pronounced differently.

According to the analysis of factual materials collected on the Zarafshan oasis, the analysis revealed that the ancient dialects of the region are dominated by ancient words. When the lexical structure of the dialects of this region is studied in comparison with ancient written sources such as "Diwani lugat at turk" (Mahmud Kashgari), "Vocabulary of Central Asian Tefsir of the XII-XIII centuries" (A.K.Borovkov), many lexical units of that period are still in the dialects of this region can be seen being used. This means that "the main part of the linguistic facts in "Diwan", which is a written monument of the XI century, is preserved in the dialects of the modern Uzbek

language belonging to the Karluk, Kipchak, Oghuz dialects" [3, pp.65-67]. Because, as mentioned above, many tribal names preserved among the Uzbek people today are also found among some other Turkic peoples. This is due to the fact that almost all Turkic peoples consist of a complex of ethnic groups, whose vocabulary is unique in antiquity. In the study of the ethnic history of the Turkic peoples, including the Uzbeks, as noted above, Mahmud Kashgari's work "Diwani lugat at-turk" has a special place. The book provides information on the linguistic and ethnic composition of the population of some towns and villages, the location of tribes and clans. "Although this work is known as a simple dictionary, it is not just a dictionary of words in the language of that time. but at the same time it gives a complete account of the phonetics, morphology of the language, the tribes, peoples, and their languages living in the vast territory of Central Asia at that time, that is, from the Upper China to the whole of Mawarannahr, Khorezm, Fergana, and Bukhara. it is a rare philological work that gives examples of various literary genres in the language of the period. Therefore, this work is extremely important for the study of the history of the peoples of Central Asia, in particular, for the study of the history of language" [4, p.29].

Many of the words used in the play are still used in our language today. The dialects of the Zarafshan oasis, which is the object of research, can be explained by this work on the basis of comparative analysis as follows:

In the Zarafshan oasis Uzbek dialects: **арқа*** (Zarafshan oasis dialects) ~ **арқа** (DLT.,I,148) – ad.orf. *orqa*; **бульг*** ~ **бульг** (DLT.,I,336) - ad.orf. *bulut*; **бълак***// **бълай*** ~ **бълак** (DLT.,I,366) – ad.orf. *bilak*; **сач*** ~ **сач** (DLT.,I,311) – ad.orf. *soch*; **бақа*** ~ **бақа** (DLT.,II,246); **таш*** ~ **таш** (DLT.,III,166) – ad.orf. *tosh*; **тохсон*** ~ **тохсон** (DLT., I,410) – ad.orf. *to'qson*; **қулач*** ~ **қулач** (DLT., 1,340) ~ *quloch* (ad.orf.); **сачук*** ~ **сачук** (DLT.,1,362) ~ *sochiq* (ad.orf.); **қанат*** ~ **қанат** (DLT.,1,398) ~ *qanot* (ad.orf.); **қачдъ//қочдъ** ~ **қачди** (DLT.II,11)- *qochdi* (ad.orf.); **севдъ***~ **сэвди** (DLT.,II,22) ~ *sevdi* (ad.orf.); **чокдъ***~ **чокдъ** (DLT.II,27) ~ *cho'kdi* (ad.orf.); **қдбдрдъ//қавардъ*** ~ **қабарди** (DLT.,II,75) ~ *qavardi* (ad.orf.); **сдвурдъ // савирди***~ **савурди** (DLT.,II,86) ~ *sovurdi* (ad.orf.); **сатишди // сотышдъ*** ~ **сатишди** (DLT.,II,94) ~ *sotishdi* (ad.orf.); **бағланди // боғләнди*** ~ **бағланди** (DLT., II 277) ~ *bog'landi*; **жирак //йирак//йироқ** ~ **жірақ** (DLT.,III,35) ~ *uzoq* (ad.orf.); **соз//сўз*** ~ **соз** – (DLT., III,136) ~ *so'z* (ad.orf.); **тул***~**тул** : **тул урағут** ~ *beva xotin* (DLT.,III,147) – *tul* (ad.orf.); **бар*** ~ **бар** (DLT., III,161) ~ *bor* (ad.orf.); **баш*** ~ **баш** (DLT., III, 165) ~ *bosh* (ad.orf.); **тағ*** ~ **тағ** (DLT., III, 167) ~ *tog'* (ad.orf.); **белалдъ** ~ **бэләлді** (DLT.,III,213) ~ *belandi* (ad.orf.); **буғдәй*** ~ **буғдај** (DLT., III, 258) ~ *bug'doy* (ad.orf.); **йумурта***~**жумуртға** (DLT.,III,439) ~ *tuxum* (ad.orf.) and other words. It can be said that "the main part of the linguistic facts in "Diwan", a written monument of the XI century, is more preserved in the dialects of the Karluk, Kipchak, Oghuz dialects of the Uzbek language than in the modern Uzbek literary language" [3, pp. 65-67]. A comparative study of the dialects of the region with one of the oldest written monuments, the "Vocabulary of Central Asian Tefsir of the XII-XIII centuries", showed that the peculiarities of the Uzbek lexicon of the XI-XII centuries are still present in these dialects.

аз* ~ ad.orf. oz; аз – (“Tefsir”, 4); **ана*** ~ ad.orf. ona; ана – (“Tefsir”, 51); **аччи*** ~ ad.orf. *achchiq*, ачи – (“Tefsir” 6); **сувар*** ~ ad.orf. *sug'ormoq*; сувар – (“Tefsir”, 276); **ақсақ*** ~ ақсақ («Tefsir», 39) ~ *oqsoq* (ad.orf.); **алдақчъ*** ~ алдақчи («Tefsir», 47) ~ *aldoqchi* (ad.orf.); **дйџғ*** ~ ајак («Tefsir», 44) ~ *oyoq* (ad.orf.); **бъчџқ*** ~ бічақ («Tefsir», 105) ~ *pichoq* (ad.orf.); **йабан*** ~ јабан («Tefsir», 130) ~ *dala* (ad.orf.); **кут*** ~ кут («Tefsir», 219) ~ ана азим кут бармиш арди (DLT, 139, II) ~ *boylik, baxt* (ad.orf.); **сару*** ~ сару («Tefsir», 262) ~ *sariq* (ad.orf.); **сувар*** ~ ad.orf. *sug'ormoq*; сувар – (“Tefsir”, 276); **там*** (Қизилча) ~ там («Tefsir», 283) ~ *uy ma'nosida* (ad.orf.); **табақ*** ~ таоқ, табақ (“Tefsir”, 280) – ad.orf. *tarelka* and others.

Although such words were historically common to Turkic languages, later on the basis of the development of each language, specific words appeared and developed.

Based on the comparison of the lexical structure of the Uzbek dialects of the Zarafshan oasis with the Turkic languages, it is possible to see the commonality between them in the example of words used with some phonetic changes. 767]. According to the results of the research, the main part of the dictionary of dialects of the region are all-Turkic words. This can be illustrated by comparing it with the Turkic languages as follows.

For example:

эдэш (-мәғ –мақ)	ad.orf. <i>adash</i> (-moq) < (от-дош) compare: -мақ ad.orf. адаш(моқ) < (от-дош) compare: Old Turkic language адаś (дўст, ўртоқ) DLT. адаш, бошқ. адаш, озарб. адаш, олт. адаш, тат. адаш, қоз. адас, хак. адас, қирғ. аяш, туркман атдаш, уйғур атдаш (friend), турк. адас, ёқут. атас (friend), тоф. адаś, тув. атташ, чулм аташ.
эйър (-мақ)	ad.orf. <i>ayir</i> (moq); compare: Old Turkic language <i>adir, abir, adar</i> DLT. әзрі, тув. адир, туркм. айыр, турк. ауір, хак. азыр, олт. айры, айыр, қорач. айыр, бошқ. айыр, қозоқ. айыр, нўғ. айыр, татар. аер, айғ. айри, тоф. аҫар.
эръғ// арук	ad.orf. <i>arig</i> . compare. DLT. аріқ, қораим. арыкъ, туркм. арық, а:рық, қирғ. арық, қоз. аріқ, нўғ. арик, қорақапок. арық, тат. арық, бошқ. арық,, олт. арық, тув. арық,, хак. арығ, уйғ. эриқ, ёқут. ары.
эръслән	ad.orf. <i>arislon</i> ; compare: DLT. арслон, туркм. арслан, қарақалпоқ. арыслан, нўғ. арслан, олт. арслан, бошқ. арыслан, хак. алаберыс, (<але парыс), қоз. арыстан, қирғ. арыстан, чув. аръслан, тув. арзылан, турк. aslan, озорб. аслан.
бәрчә	ad.orf. <i>barcha</i> , compare; кад. турк. варса, хак. парчан, татар. барча, туркм. барча, қирғ. барча, уйғ. барча, қоз. барша, қорақалпоқ. барша, нўғ. барчша, тоф. барśa.
бултър // бълтър	ad.orf. <i>bultur</i> ; compare. озарб. билдир (былдыр), қирғ. былтыр, қоз. былтыр, ойр. былтыр, бошқ. былтыр, тат. былтыр, оль. пылтыр, хак. пылтыр, чув. пѐлтѐр (last year).
Бөрь	ad.orf. <i>bo'ri</i> ; compare: Old Turkic language <i>bori</i> , олт. бору, тув. бѐру, хак. пўўр, ёқут. бѐре, туркм. бѐри, бошқ. буре, тат. буре, қоз. борі, қирғ. бѐру, уйғ. бѐрә.

Йетгъ // йедъ	ad.orf. yetti; compare: Old Turkic language jēti, jedi, DLT. jētī, олт. jēti, тув. чеди, хак. чити, ёкут. сэтгэ, озарб. једді, туркм. йеди, бошқ. йете, тат. жиде, қоз. жеті, қорақалпоқ. жети, қирғ. жети, уйғ. йетте, тоф. hsedī, қум. етти, нўғ. йети, чув. җиччѐ, җич, җичѐ.
Йәлғыз// йәлғуз //Йәлғыз	ad.orf. yolg'iz, Old Turkic language jañus, jalañuz, jalñuz, jabñuz, jalañuz, олт. jañыс, тув. чаңгыс, хак. галғыз, озарб. јалғыз, туркм. йалғыз, тат. йалғыз, бошқ. йаңғыз, қоз. жалғыз, қирғ. жалғыз, жаңғыз, уйғ. йалғуз, қораим. йальғыз, йилыңғыз, йалыңғыз.
Йәмғур// йәмғър	ad.orf. yomg'ir; compare: DLT. jaғmir, қораим. йағъмур, йамьгур, йангъур, йаньгур, уйғ. йамгур, чулм. йамгур, чамгур, тат. йағир, нўғ. йамгыр, бошқ. йамгыр, қирғ. жамғыр, қорақалпоқ. жамғыр, қоз. жанбыр, қум. йангур, қорач. джангур, олт. дванмыр, хак. нақмыр, ёкут. самныр, чув. сумәр, сол.хор. йағыш.
Ылғарь	ad.orf. ilgari; compare: туркм. илери, гаг. илери, қораим. илери, қирғ. илгери, нўғ. илгери, қорақалпоқ. илгери, қоз. илгері, тат. илгери, бошқ. илгери, уйғ. илгари, турк. ileri.
Йығьрмә // Йыйьрмә// Жыйьрмә	ad.orf. йигирма; compare: Old Turkic language igirmā, jiyirmā, уйғ. жигирме, қум. ийирма, озарб. игирмә, туркм. йигрими, қорач. чийирме, нўғ. йырма, қирғ. жийирми, қоз. жіјірмі, қорақалпоқ. жигерма, тув. чээрби, хак. чибирги, ёкут. сүүрбэ, чув. җирѐм.
Йьрьй // ьрьй	ad.orf. yirik; compare: туркм. і:ри, қирғ. ири, нўғ. ири, қорақалпоқ. ири, қоз. ірі, озарб. ири, тат. ири, бошқ. ири, уйғ. ирик, йирик.
Кепәй	ad.orf. керак; compare: DLT. кәпәк, ойр. кеп. хак. кип. тув. хеп, қирғ. кебек, қоз. кебек, туркм. кебек, қорақалпоқ. кебек, нўғ. кебик, қум. гебек, озарб. кәпәк, уйғ. кепәк, тат. кибек, бошқ. кебек, чув. кипек, кирѐк (қазғок), сол. мўғул. кебек.
Кесәй	ad.orf. kesak; compare: қирғ. кесек, қоз. кесек, уйғ. кесәк, нўғ. кесек, қкм. гысек, бошқ. кисәк, тат. кисәк, хак. кизек, чув. каҗак, чулм. кәзәк.
Кыйыз	ad.orf. kigiz; compare: DLT. kijiz, қирғ. кийиз, нўғ. кийиз, хак. киис, бошқ. кейез, қоз. кігіз, олт. кийис, хак. киис, бошқ. кейез, тат. Кийез, тув. кидис, чув. кѐсҗѐ, чулм. кис, ки:с.
Кыйык	ad.orf. kiyik; compare: Old Turkic language kәjik. DLT. kәjik (ёввойи хайвонлар), уйғ. кийик (тоғ эчикиси), қирғ. кийик, қораим. кийик, ойр. кийик, бошқ. кеек (йиртқич хайвон), хак. кийк (ёввойи эчки), тат.киек (ёввойи куш), чув. кайик (ёввойи хайвон).
Кындык	ad.orf. kindik; compare: ёкут. кин, қимрғ. киндик, члм. киндиг, бошқ. кендек, чув. кѐнтѐк.
Кыйәв	ad.orf. kuyov; compare: Old Turkic language kыдачұ, кызачұ, хұдачұ, гыйәгұ, уйғ. куйа, ўғил, озарб. күрәкән, туркм. кәрекен, гийев, гаг. чува, қум. гийев, қирғ. куйөө, қорач. куйеу, қоз. кујеу, қорақалпоқ. куйеу, нўғ. киев, бошқ. кейәу, тат. кийәу, олт. куйу, куйе, тув. кудэә, хак. киде, кузэә, шор. кузэ, ёкут. кутуө, чув. кѐрұ<кѐрѐв.
Кокрәй	ad.orf. ko'krak; compare: DLT. кәкүз, уйғ. көкрәк, қирғ. көкурок, қорақалпоқ. кокрек, қоз. көкрек, қорач. көкрек, нўғ. кокирек, олт. кегус, хак. көгис, тув. хөрек, қум. көкюрек, чув. кәкәр, гаг. гус (<гогус), туркм. кукурек, бошқ. кукрек.
Сыйрәй	ad.orf. siyrak; compare: DLT, сәзрәк, озарб. сейрәк, турк. сейрек, қирғ.

	сейрек, қоз. сирек, қорақалпоқ. сирек, нұғ. сийрек, қум.сийрек, тат. сирек, бошқ. һирәк, олт. сайақ, хак. сайақ, сайрах.
суйәй	ad.orf. suyak; compare: Old Turkic language söküк, тув. сөөк, ёкут. уңдох, озарб. сумун, туркм. сунк, тат. сөйәк, бошқ. һөйәк, қоз. суек, нұғ. суйёк, қум. суйек, қирғ. сөөк, уйғ. суйек, олт. соок, тоф. сә:к.
тҗнглә (мәф) // тыңла (моқ)	ad.orf. tingla(-moq) compare: Old Turkic language tiŋla, бошқ. тйуңла, тат. тйуңла, уйғ. тингши, хак. дыңна, қоз. тиңла, озарб. динла, туркм. динле, қум. тынла, қирғ. тыңша.
узәф // узәк	ad.orf. uzoq; compare: DLT. узақ, уйғ. узақ, туркм. узақ, қирғ. узақ, қоз. узақ, қорақалпоқ. узақ, қум.узақ, нұғ. узақ, тат. озақ, бошқ. озақ, чув. варах, озарб. узах.
чўләғ	ad.orf. cho'loq; compare: уйғ. чолак, туркм. чолак, қирғ. чолоқ, қоз. шолак, қорақалпоқ. шолак, озарб. чолаг, тат. чулак, бошқ. сулак, чув. чалах.
Йулдуз	ad.orf. yulduz; compare Old Turkic language julduz, қум. йўлдуз, уйғ. йолдуз, жолдуз, озарб. улдуз, туркм. йылдыз, гаг. йылдыз, тат. йолдыз, бошқ. йолдоз, қирғ. жылдыз, қоз. жулдыз, қорақалпоқ. жылдыз, нұғ. йўлдуз, қорач. джулдыз, тув. сылдыс, ёкут. сулус, хак. чылдыс, чув. çältär.
йумшәғ йумшәк	ad.orf. yumshoq; compare: Old Turkic language jimsäq, DLT, јумшақ, туркм. йумшәк, озарб. јумшәг, уйғ. жумшақ, қирғ. жумшақ, қоз. жумсақ, нұғ. йумсақ, бошқ. йомшәк, тат. йомшәк, олт. увымчак, хак. нымзах, чув. йамшак.
йәрәм	ad.orf. ярим; compare: нұғ. йарты, йарым, тат. йарты, бошқ. йарты, қирғ. жарым, қоз. жарым, уйғ. йерим, хак. чарым, чув. сурә, сур, сурма.
Ойын	ad.orf. o'yin compare: Old Turkic language ojuŋ, тув. ойун, қирғ. ойун, туркм. ойун, озарб. ојун, хак. ойын, нұғ. ойын, олт. ойын, қоз. ойын, ёкут. оонньюу, бошқ. уйын, тат. уиен, уйғ. ойан, чув. вайа, вай, тоф. зен.
ордәк	ad.orf. o'rdak; compare: Old Turkic language ödräk, ödiräk, DLT. өртөк, тув. одурек, хак. өртек, озарб. өрдәк, туркм. өрдәк, қорақалпоқ. ордек, уйғ. ө(р)дәк, ёкут. өрдукээн, гаг. йөрдек, бошқ. ойрәк, тат. урдәк, қоз. уйрек, қирғ. өрдөк.

Such words belonging to the lexical layer of each Turkic language have been expanded over a long period of time as a result of the internal development of the language, and its vocabulary has been enriched with new words. Later, they formed their own dictionary of each Turkic language. Undoubtedly, the comparative study of the lexicon of Uzbek dialects of the studied Zarafshan oasis can provide valuable materials in determining the historical development of our language, the basis for obtaining the necessary information about our national values. The ethnolinguistic and etymological analysis of the lexicon of Uzbek dialects, including the Uzbek dialects of the Zarafshan oasis, provides the necessary information not only for the history of the Uzbek language, but also for the science of Turkology.

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